

Pyrolytic Carbon Microlattices from 3D-Printed Polyethylene Glycol Diacrylate and their In Vitro Assessment for Bone Regeneration

Monsur Islam,* Jesús Ordoño, Wei Tang, Miguel Monclús, Mónica Echeverry-Rendón, and De-Yi Wang*

This study investigates the potential of 3D pyrolytic carbon (PyC) scaffolds, derived from 3D-printed polyethylene glycol diacrylate (PEGDA) lattices, for bone tissue engineering. The pyrolytic conversion of PEGDA is systematically studied, which shows that the pyrolysis temperature significantly influences the structural and material properties of the resulting PyC materials. The scaffolds exhibit tunable electrical conductivity and mechanical strength, with the conductivity increasing by seven orders of magnitude as the pyrolysis temperature rises from 500 to 900 °C. Similarly, mechanical properties improve with temperature, reaching a maximum elastic modulus of 36.87 ± 2.95 GPa and hardness of 5.4 ± 0.42 GPa at 900 °C. The 3D PyC microlattices support MC3T3-E1 preosteoblast proliferation and promote osteogenic differentiation, as evidenced by the expression of key markers (ALP, Runx2, OCN, and Col1A1). Among the scaffolds, PyC obtained at 500 °C shows the highest metabolic activity attributed to their oxygen-rich surface chemistry, while those treated at 900 °C induce the most robust differentiation, driven by enhanced stiffness and mechanotransductive signaling. These findings position 3D-printed PyC scaffolds as promising, tunable platforms for bone tissue regeneration, combining structural integrity with cell-instructive properties.

scaffolds include polymers, ceramics, metals, and composites.^[1,2] However, despite significant advancements, current scaffold materials still face several limitations. Polymers, which typically offer excellent processability and biocompatibility, often suffer from mechanical mismatch due to their significantly lower mechanical properties compared to native bones. For instance, typical values of mechanical stiffness of polymers are below 100 MPa, compared to 15–40 GPa for natural bone.^[3,4] Ceramic materials, including alumina or hydroxyapatite, exhibit brittle behaviors and feature low fracture toughness, restricting their use in dynamically loaded environments.^[5] In addition to mechanical properties, conventional scaffolds often fail to recreate the intricate porous micro-architecture of native bone, which is essential for vascularization, nutrient diffusion, and osteointegration. These challenges highlight the need for an alternative material

1. Introduction

Bone tissue engineering has emerged as a promising strategy to address critical-size bone defects, which remain a critical challenge in orthopedic medicine. Over the past decades, various scaffold-based approaches have been investigated to facilitate bone regeneration, where the scaffolds aim to provide a temporary extracellular matrix for supporting cell adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation for the formation of new bone tissue. Popular choices of materials for fabricating these

platform that can simultaneously achieve the necessary mechanical robustness, bioactivity, and precise structural design.

The family of carbon-based materials represents a highly adaptable portfolio of biomaterials due to their biocompatibility and surface chemistry, which can be tailored to bone regeneration. These materials, particularly carbon nanotubes and graphene, have shown exceptional promise in mitigating mechanical mismatches and offering advanced biocompatibility, positioning them as promising candidates for innovative bone tissue engineering solutions.^[6,7] Despite their early and rigorous investigation for musculoskeletal repair, the full potential of these carbon materials in this field remains largely untapped. A primary limitation is their processability due to their nanomaterial nature, which often requires embedding in polymeric matrices, impeding the development of three-dimensional porous structures essential for scaffold applications.^[3,8] This results in a composite where the properties of the polymeric components prevail over those of carbon materials, leading to suboptimal outcomes in tissue engineering contexts.

To overcome the limitations of carbon nanomaterials-based scaffolds, we propose the use of 3D-printed pyrolytic carbon (PyC) microlattices as an architected scaffold platform for bone tissue engineering. The typical process for 3D architected PyC

M. Islam, J. Ordoño, W. Tang, M. Monclús, M. Echeverry-Rendón, D.-Y. Wang
IMDEA Materials Institute
Calle Eric Kandel, 2, 28906 Getafe, Madrid, Spain
E-mail: monsur.islam@imdea.org; deyi.wang@imdea.org

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includes 3D printing of a photocurable epoxy resin, followed by pyrolysis at high temperatures (typically ≥ 500 °C).^[9] This process results in a free-standing carbon architecture with substantial geometric shrinkage (60%–90%) that retains the precise architecture of the original printed structure but with structural features significantly smaller than the printed ones.^[9] The structural resolution can surpass the precision and complexity possible with polymers, metals, or ceramics. Additionally, PyC's compatibility with magnetic resonance imaging, due to the low abundance of nuclear magnetic resonance sensitive ^{13}C within PyC (<1%),^[10] makes it a highly favorable material for clinical monitoring, offering noninvasive imaging of the scaffold's integration with bone tissue, an advantage lacking in most metallic implants and polymeric composites.

Despite these promising attributes, the potential of 3D-printed PyC in bone tissue engineering remains largely unexplored. Even though previous studies provided preliminary evidence of cytocompatibility of 3D PyC materials,^[11,12] their ability to support osteogenesis and promote bone regeneration has not been investigated. Moreover, a critical challenge in these studies was the use of commercially available photocurable resins, which are proprietary formulations with unknown compositions. The pyrolytic conversion of these resins significantly affects the final scaffold size, porosity, and mechanical properties, and often leads to the formation of noncarbon impurities^[13] due to the use of additives within the resin. These factors hinder reproducibility, scalability, and optimization of PyC scaffolds for biomedical applications.

In this work, we introduce 3D-printed PyC microlattice architectures as a novel, structurally tunable, biocompatible scaffold system for in vitro bone tissue engineering. To address the uncertainties associated with commercial resins, we establish a reproducible and chemically defined fabrication route using polyethylene glycol diacrylate (PEGDA), a well-characterized material widely used in biomedical applications,^[14] as the photocurable resin precursor for PyC.^[14] The pyrolytic conversion of 3D-printed PEGDA is categorically studied to investigate its influence on the overall structural dimensions, surface chemistry, and mechanical and electrical properties. Finally, we assess the in vitro biological response of MC3T3-E1 preosteoblast cells within 3D PyC scaffolds to evaluate their potential for supporting cell adhesion, proliferation, and osteogenic differentiation. This study presents the first comprehensive in vitro evaluation of 3D-printed PEGDA-derived PyC scaffolds for bone regeneration, offering new insights into their structural advantages, biocompatibility, and potential as a next-generation material platform in bone tissue engineering.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Carbonization of 3D-Printed PEGDA

We employed digital light processing (DLP) 3D printing to fabricate the precursor PEGDA structures. Details of the fabrication process are provided in the experimental section. Briefly, the scaffold featured an octet lattice unit cell (inset of **Figure 1a**) with a size of 1.2 mm and a lattice strut diameter of 200 μm . The strut diameter was chosen based on the smallest dimension reliably achieved with our 3D printing system. The printed PEGDA structures were

carbonized at different temperatures, ranging from 410 to 900 °C, to achieve PyC microlattice architectures. The pyrolyzed samples are referred to as "CX" in the manuscript, where "X" represents the pyrolysis temperatures. Representative images of fabricated PEGDA and PyC architectures are presented in **Figure 1a**. **Figure S1**, Supporting Information further shows the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the printed PEGDA microlattices, depicting a wrinkly surface, perhaps arising from the drying and curing process. After pyrolysis, the resulting PyC microlattices retained identical geometrical features of the precursor PEGDA without any visible structural deformities (**Figure 1b**). Closer inspection revealed a near-smooth surface morphology of the PyC microlattices, as illustrated in **Figure 1c**, even though the printing layer artifacts remained visible along the lattice length.

It should be noted here that a drastic geometrical shrinkage occurred during the carbonization process, which is expected due to the thermochemical decomposition of the precursor and the release of gaseous byproducts from the precursor matrix. The degree of shrinkage highly depends on the chemical composition of the precursor, the initial lattice dimension, and the pyrolysis temperature.^[15–17] As the precursor chemical composition and initial lattice geometry were consistent in this work, we investigated the effect of pyrolysis temperature on the shrinkage. Expectedly, as pyrolysis temperature increased, the lattice thickness of the resulting PyC structures decreased, leading to higher shrinkage, as shown in **Figures 1d,e**, respectively. Specifically, the lattice thickness reduced from 35.0 ± 1.7 μm at 410 °C to 23.3 ± 0.9 μm at 900 °C, translating to an increase in shrinkage from $82.5\% \pm 0.8\%$ to $88.3\% \pm 0.5\%$. The degree of shrinkage of PEGDA was considerably higher than that of commercial resins, which generally exhibit 50%–80% shrinkage.^[18,19] The additional reinforcement with additives could be attributed to the lower shrinkage in commercial resins.

Since shrinkage is driven by the thermal degradation of the precursor, which ultimately determines the final dimension and properties of the resulting PyC structures, we studied the thermal degradation process by performing thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of 3D-printed PEGDA and analyzing the evolved gases during this degradation by real-time Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). **Figure 1f** shows the TGA and the derivative thermogravimetry (DTG) curves of printed PEGDA, which revealed that the thermal decomposition of PEGDA majorly occurred between 305 and 450 °C, attributing to a major weight loss of $\approx 96\%$. The maximum mass loss rate was observed at around 410 °C. The weight loss profile further guided the carbonization protocol used in this work. For example, based on the decomposition behavior observed in TGA, the temperature for stabilization and first isothermal heating was chosen at 300 °C, just below the decomposition onset temperature (305 °C). The second isothermal heating was performed at 410 °C to allow complete release of the volatile gaseous byproducts, further facilitating better structural stability of the resulting PyC material. Considering the thermal degradation pattern of PEGDA, the lowest pyrolysis temperature chosen in this study was 410 °C.

The real-time FTIR spectra of the evolved gases throughout the entire heat treatment process are presented in **Figure 1g**, whereas the FTIR spectrum of the volatile species at the maximum decomposition rate (at ≈ 410 °C) is shown in **Figure 1h**. The characteristic

Figure 1. a) A digital photograph of 3D-printed microlattice architectures with octet unit cells before (left) and after (right) pyrolysis, highlighting the drastic geometric shrinkage after pyrolysis. The inset at the bottom left corner shows the design of the octet unit cell. b) SEM image of PyC microlattices, depicting the retention of the original precursor design. c) High-magnification SEM image of an individual PyC lattice element. d) The variation of lattice thickness with pyrolysis temperature. e) The shrinkage of lattice thickness as a function of pyrolysis temperature. f) TGA and DTG of precursor PEGDA, showing the thermal degradation behavior. g) Real-time FTIR spectra of the gases evolved during the pyrolysis of PEGDA. h) FTIR spectra of the evolved gases at the point of maximum deposition.

gas signals from PEGDA decomposition included 2924, 2895, and 2880 cm^{-1} ($-\text{CH}_2$, CH, CH_3), 2358 and 2320 cm^{-1} (CO_2), 2170 cm^{-1} (CO), 1750 cm^{-1} (C=O), 1129 cm^{-1} (C-O), and 945 cm^{-1} (O-C-O or ethane).^[20,21]

TGA and real-time FTIR of the evolved gases provided an insight into the pyrolysis mechanism of 3D-printed PEGDA. Based on these results, the following processes could be anticipated. In the initial degradation phase, the cleavage of ester (C-O) and ether (O-C-O) bonds initiated the breakdown of the polymer network, leading to the release of oxygenated fragments, as suggested by the C-O stretching peak at 1129 cm^{-1} and O-C-O vibrations at 945 cm^{-1} .^[22] Subsequently, rapid decarboxylation and decarbonylation reactions resulted in the release of CO_2 (2358 and 667 cm^{-1}) and CO (2170 cm^{-1}).^[23]

The presence of a strong C=O stretching peak at 1750 cm^{-1} suggests the formation of aldehydes, ketones, or anhydrides as intermediate degradation products.^[22] Simultaneously, the β -scission of aliphatic chains led to the release of hydrocarbon species,^[24] confirmed by the CH_2 and CH_3 stretching peaks at 2924 and 2880 cm^{-1} , as well as the ethane-related vibrations at 945 cm^{-1} . The fact that all major peaks reached their highest intensity at $\approx 410^\circ\text{C}$ indicates a rapid and simultaneous release of volatile compounds at this temperature. As the temperature increased beyond 450 $^\circ\text{C}$, most volatile species almost diminished, leading to the progressive densification of the material. However, C-O stretching signals ($\approx 1100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) persisted even above 500 $^\circ\text{C}$, suggesting that some oxygen functionalities remained in the carbonized framework. The retention of C-O functionalities beyond 500 $^\circ\text{C}$ indicates

that certain oxygen-containing groups, such as ethers or phenols, were more thermally stable. Upon further increase in temperature, progressive dehydrogenation and elimination of residual oxygenated groups occurred, enhancing the structural integrity of the material.

2.2. Raman Analysis of 3D PyC

We performed Raman spectroscopy of fabricated PyC structures to assess the materials characteristics of the obtained carbon materials. The Raman spectra of PyC structures pyrolyzed at different temperatures (Figure 2a) exhibited two characteristic peaks around 1350 and 1590 cm^{-1} , which are attributed to D and G peaks, respectively, and traditionally correspond to disordered carbon and graphitic carbon, respectively.^[25,26] The intensity ratio of these peaks (I_D/I_G) is typically considered an indicator of the degree of graphitization, where a lower intensity ratio suggests a higher degree of graphitic ordering. For instance, pure graphene ideally should have an intensity ratio of zero.^[27] Interestingly, in our study, the intensity ratio increased with pyrolysis temperature (Figure S2a, Supporting Information),

which contradicts the conventional expectation that higher temperatures enhance graphitic order. This counterintuitive behavior reflects the limitations of using intensity ratios alone, particularly for nongraphitizing or low-temperature pyrolyzed carbons, where band overlaps and structural heterogeneity can distort interpretation.

To address this limitation and gain deeper insight into the material characteristics, we performed peak deconvolutions of the Raman spectra using Voigt peak fitting to incorporate both Gaussian and Lorentz peak features. As a result of fitting trials, it was found that four peaks, two peaks for each D and G peaks, and a linear background were necessary to reproduce the spectral data for all the samples. These four peaks were assigned as D_1 at $\approx 1230 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, D_2 at $\approx 1350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, G_1 at 1600 cm^{-1} , and G_2 at $\approx 1530 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, as summarized in Table 1. Representative curve-fitting and peak assignments are presented in Figure 2b for the PyC samples obtained at 500 and 900 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, while the rest of the curve fittings are presented in Figures S2b-e, Supporting Information.

To evaluate the effect of pyrolysis temperature, we plotted the area ratios of A_{D_1}/A_G and A_{D_2}/A_G in Figure 2c, as these can provide valuable insight into the evolving microstructure of the PyC

Figure 2. a) Raman spectra of PyC materials obtained at different pyrolysis temperatures. b) Representative curve fittings and peak assignments after deconvolution of Raman spectra of PyC materials at 900 and 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. c) The area ratio of deconvoluted peaks as a function of pyrolysis temperature. d) XPS survey spectra of 3D PyC spectra at different pyrolysis temperatures. Deconvolution of e) C1s and f) O1s high-resolution spectra for identifying the functional groups present in the PyC materials.

Table 1. Summary of the peak assignments of deconvoluted Raman spectra.

Peak assignment	Peak position [cm ⁻¹]	Description	Ref.
D ₁	1230	Aryl-alkyl ether; <i>para</i> -aromatics; small polyaromatic hydrocarbons	[28,29]
D ₂	1350	Traditional D-band, corresponding to the A _{1g} mode and indicating an in-plane breathing vibration associated with the disorder in the carbon matrix; C–C between aromatic rings and aromatics with not less than 6 rings	[25,26]
G ₁	1600	Conventional G-band, corresponding to the Raman-active E _{2g} in-plane vibration mode, signifying graphitic carbon.	[25,26]
G ₂	1530	Aromatics with 3–5 rings in adjacent 6-membered rings	[28,29]

materials. Here, A_G is the sum of A_{G1} and A_{G2}, as both peaks contribute to the graphitization of the carbon material. The A_{D1}/A_G ratio reflects the qualitative presence of aliphatic or oxygenated components present in the PyC materials, whereas A_{D2}/A_G represents the qualitative amount of carbon aromatics, as the D₂ band is still associated with the aromatic domains of the carbon materials. Other researchers have already applied similar approaches while investigating pyrolyzed hydrocarbons.^[28–31]

The ratio of A_{D1}/A_G decreased significantly from 410 to 500 °C, followed by a gradual decline until 700 °C, beyond which it reached a steady state. This behavior aligns with the TGA result (Figure 1f), which showed that the thermal degradation of PEGDA completes around 450 °C. The PyC obtained at 410 °C likely retained substantial amounts of residual aliphatic and oxygenated components within a carbon-rich matrix, leading to a high A_{D1}/A_G ratio. Upon increasing the temperature to 500 °C, most of these residual components decomposed, resulting in a sharp decline in the A_{D1}/A_G ratio. At this point, the PyC material might still have residual hydrocarbons or other heteroatoms, which continued to release with increasing pyrolysis temperatures, as also suggested by the thermogravimetric analysis coupled with Fourier transformation infrared spectroscopy (TG-FTIR) of the gaseous byproducts (Figure 1g). Beyond 700 °C, as suggested by the stabilization of A_{D1}/A_G, most nonaromatic carbon species might have been eliminated. In contrast, the ratio of A_{D2}/A_G increased steadily with pyrolysis temperature, suggesting progressive aromatization of the carbon atoms within the PyC matrix. This behavior is consistent with the pyrolysis mechanism of organic precursors, where higher temperatures influence the formation and densification of polycyclic aromatic structures through carbon atom self-organization.^[32–34]

2.3. X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) Analysis of 3D PyC

The findings from the Raman analysis were further corroborated by XPS. The XPS survey spectra (Figure 2d) mainly featured dominant peaks of C1s and O1s, with decreasing peak intensity

of O1s with pyrolysis temperature. Quantitative elemental analysis revealed that the atomic ratio C:O increased from 88.1:11.8 at 500 °C to 93.8:6.2 at 700 °C to 96.7:3.3 at 900 °C, confirming a progressive elimination of oxygen-containing components during pyrolysis.

To further understand the chemical bonding states, C1s high-resolution spectra were deconvoluted into five characteristic peaks, as shown in Figure 2e. The primary peak at 284.5 ± 0.1 eV corresponds to sp²-hybridized polyaromatic carbons (C=C), indicative of graphitic structure,^[35,36] which became more pronounced with increasing pyrolysis temperature. A secondary peak around 285.0 ± 0.2 eV, corresponding to aliphatic carbon (C–C/C–H), could also be deciphered, which exhibited a strong presence at 500 °C with declining contributions at higher temperatures. The trend of both peaks with temperature signifies the progressive graphitization with increasing temperatures, which agrees with the findings from the Raman analysis.

Oxygen-containing functionalities were identified at 285.9 ± 0.1 eV (C–O from hydroxyl or ether groups) and 287.9 ± 0.1 eV (C=O or O–C–O, characteristic of carbonyl, carboxyl, or ester groups).^[36] These peaks also showed a decreasing contribution with increasing pyrolysis temperature, signifying gradual carbonization and loss of surface polarity. Additionally, a shake-up satellite feature at 290.6 ± 0.1 eV, arising from π–π* transitions in aromatic rings, further confirmed the presence of conjugated sp²-carbon domains, particularly for 700 and 900 °C.

To identify the oxygen-containing surface functional groups of the PyC materials, we deconvoluted the O1s spectra into three distinct peaks (Figure 2f). The most pronounced oxygen-containing peak in all the samples was around 533.2 ± 0.1 eV, which is associated with the hydroxyl or ether group (C–O).^[37] A second prominent peak at 532.1 ± 0.1 eV could be attributed to carbonyl oxygen atoms (C=O) in esters, amides, and carboxylic anhydrides.^[38,39] The peak at 531.3 ± 0.1 eV corresponds to C=O groups (ketone, lactone, carbonyl), typically associated with oxidized graphitic edges and defect sites. The C=O groups had a strong contribution in the PyC sample at 500 °C, demonstrating a high surface polarity. However, these contributions progressively decreased with increasing temperature, as presented in Figure S3, Supporting Information, mirroring the elemental trend from the survey spectra. It should be noted that the remnant organic components within the carbon matrix also contributed to the strong presence of oxygen-containing functional groups at 500 °C. On the contrary, the oxygen functional groups detected in PyC at 700 and 900 °C could be mostly from the surface of the material, due to the exposure of the material to the air.

2.4. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) Analysis of 3D PyC

We performed TEM of 3D PyC samples to evaluate their microstructural evolution as a function of pyrolysis temperature. The high-resolution TEM image of sample C500 (Figure 3a) revealed that the material predominantly exhibited an amorphous carbon network, with a few numbers of short-range graphitic domains dispersed within the matrix. The graphitic domains became more prominent as the temperature increased to 700 °C,

Figure 3. TEM images of PyC materials obtained at a) 500 °C, b) 700 °C, and c) 900 °C. The inset of (b) shows a zoomed-in contrast-enhanced image of the rectangular section marked, highlighting the formation of cage-like structures. The subimages of (c) include the zoomed-in and contrast-enhanced images of points 1 and 2 marked in (c). Subimage 1 shows the interlattice distances of graphitic layers, while 2 shows curved graphitic layers induced by fullerene-like structures.

featuring longer chain lengths, as observed in the high-resolution TEM of C700 (Figure 3b). However, the overall matrix still remained mostly amorphous, suggesting that full reorganization of the carbon atoms was yet to be achieved at this stage. Interestingly, several near-spherical or closed cage-like features emerged in the microstructure of C700, as highlighted in the inset of Figure 3b. Sharma et al. previously reported the formation of such cage-like structures while performing in situ pyrolysis of an epoxy resin under TEM, referring to them as “fullerene-like” structures.^[33] They discovered that these fullerene-like structures emerged around 600 °C due to the curvature in graphene fragments in the presence of nonsix-membered rings (point defects). A similar phenomenon might have occurred in our study during the pyrolysis of 3D-printed PEGDA. These fullerene-like structures featured a diameter of around 1–2 nm, which is in agreement with previously reported studies.^[33,34]

At 900 °C, the PyC material exhibited a further increase in the graphitic ordering, as observed in the TEM image of C900 (Figure 3c). This agreed with the higher degree of graphitization as characterized by the Raman spectra. The material featured improved graphitic layers with an interlayer spacing of 0.34 nm (inset 1 of Figure 3c). However, the graphitic layers featured a turbostratic nature, unlike well-ordered graphite. Such turbostratic characteristics arose due to the misalignment and distortion of the graphene layers, which prevented them from graphitization. Notably, the fullerene-like features played an important role in forming such turbostratic microstructures. The fullerene-like structures could induce curvatures and distortions in the graphitic layers at lower temperatures, disrupting the stacking of the graphitic layers. Furthermore, they could move within the carbon

matrix, which could yield additional curvatures and defects within the graphitic layers and thereby reinforce the turbostratic microstructure.^[33,34] An example of such fullerene-induced curved graphitic layers is presented in inset 2 of Figure 3c, where several curved graphitic planes could be observed around the central fullerene-like structure. These structures are known to further prevent the carbon material from complete graphitization even at really high temperatures (>2000 °C), categorizing such carbon materials as nongraphitizing carbon.^[40,41]

2.5. Electrical Properties of 3D PyC

We measured the electrical properties of the 3D PyC structures using a two-electrode method. The results demonstrated a strong dependency of electrical conductivity on pyrolysis temperature, as presented in Figure 4a. Samples C410 and C500 exhibited extremely high electrical resistance, effectively behaving like electrically insulating materials. In fact, the resistance of C410 was beyond the measurable limit of the multimeter used, while C500 displayed an electrical conductivity in the order of 10^{-7} S m⁻¹. This could be attributed to the highly amorphous state of the carbon materials, the presence of residual aliphatic bonds, and a high concentration of heteroatoms within the matrix, as suggested by Raman and XPS analyses.

As the temperature increased, the carbon material became more electrically conductive. Increasing the temperature from 500 to 700 °C resulted in an increase in the conductivity by five orders of magnitude (from 10 to 10^{-2} S m⁻¹). This drastic enhancement could be attributed to the microstructural and compositional transformations occurring within this temperature range. The progressive elimination of heteroatoms (oxygen and hydrogen) from the carbon matrix, as evidenced by XPS, reduced the number of *sp*³-hybridized carbon sites, thereby increasing the number of *sp*² carbon sites, which are majorly responsible for electrical conductance. Furthermore, within the temperature range, the formation of graphitic planes was initiated, which were rearranged progressively with increasing temperature, as shown in the TEM images. Such increased connectivity among the graphitic domains further facilitated electron delocalization, improving the charge transport across the material.

Beyond 700 °C, the rate of improvement in conductivity slightly decreased, even though substantial improvement still occurred. At 900 °C, the conductivity reached 9.3 ± 3.8 S m⁻¹. At this stage, the predominant mechanism responsible for the conductivity enhancement was the improvement in graphitic ordering, as heteroatom eliminations were completed by this time. However, the turbostratic microstructure of the carbon materials could have restricted further improvements in electrical conductivity by obstructing the formation of long-range graphitic planes as in graphite material.

It is important to emphasize that the conductivity values reported in this study represent the effective electrical conductivity of the entire 3D microlattice structure, rather than the intrinsic conductivity of bulk PyC. Electrical conductivity ranging from 10–1000 S m⁻¹ has been reported in the literature for glassy carbon, which is a form of pyrolytic carbon, depending on the pyrolysis condition and precursor’s chemical configuration.^[42,43] In our study, the high porosity and open-lattice geometry of the

Figure 4. a) Electrical conductivity of 3D PyC microlattice architectures at different pyrolysis temperatures. b) Variation of elastic modulus and hardness of PyC materials at different pyrolysis temperatures, obtained using nanoindentation tests. c) Compressive modulus, specific modulus, and d) compressive strength of 3D PyC microlattice structures as a function of pyrolysis temperature. Data represent mean \pm SD from $n \geq 3$ specimens per group.

scaffold, as shown in Figure 1c, resulted in tortuous current pathways and reduced conductive cross-sectional area, which can substantially lower the effective conductivity.^[44,45] Additional contributions to resistance may arise from inter-strut contact points, surface roughness, and potential microporosity within the carbon struts. These architectural factors must be considered when comparing to reported conductivity values for bulk or compressed porous carbon materials of similar nominal density.

2.6. Mechanical Properties of 3D PyC

Before evaluating the mechanical behavior of 3D-printed PyC lattice structures, we first assessed the mechanical properties of the bulk material using nanoindentation tests. Similar to electrical conductivity, the mechanical properties also exhibited a strong dependence on pyrolysis temperature. Typical load-displacement curves are shown in Figure S4a, Supporting Information, where it can be clearly seen that for similar indentation loads, the indenter penetrated much deeper for samples processed at lower temperatures. The samples exhibited a superelastic behavior, recovering most of the imposed deformation, which is consistent with the fact that the indentation depth was limited to the micron range.

The elastic modulus and hardness values obtained from these tests are presented in Figure 4b. At lower pyrolysis temperatures

(410 and 500 °C), the mechanical properties remained low, with no significant difference among the samples obtained at these temperatures. A steep improvement in the mechanical properties was observed as the temperature increased up to 700 °C. Specifically, the elastic modulus increased from 6.75 ± 0.63 GPa at 500 °C to 33.87 ± 3.39 GPa at 700 °C, whereas the hardness improved from 0.86 ± 0.07 GPa to 4.79 ± 0.59 GPa. Beyond 700 °C, the improvement rate decreased substantially. While both elastic modulus and stiffness still improved, the enhancement was marginal. In fact, there was no significant difference between samples C800 and C900. At 900 °C, the elastic modulus and hardness reached 36.87 ± 2.95 GPa and 5.40 ± 0.42 GPa, respectively.

As mentioned earlier, the PyC material at 500 °C lacked graphitic domains and still contained residual organic components, limiting structural integrity and thereby resulting in low mechanical properties. With increasing temperature, the removal of heteroatoms led to a denser and stronger covalently bonded carbon network through the formation of graphitic domains and their subsequent densification. Such sp^2 carbon-dominated microstructural transformation improved the load transfer among carbon planes, resulting in substantial improvement in the mechanical properties. Beyond 700 °C, even though the graphitic domains got longer with temperature, the turbostratic microstructure of PyC might have restrained the load-bearing capability to some extent, resulting in a lower improvement rate beyond 700 °C. The pyrolysis-

dependent mechanical behavior of PyC materials could also be reflected in the indentation depth, as it decreased with pyrolysis temperature (Figure S4b), indicating the material's resistance to mechanical loading.

We further characterized the mechanical properties of 3D PyC microlattice structures using uniaxial compression tests. As expected, 3D PyC structures also exhibited a strong dependency of pyrolysis temperature on the mechanical response under compressive loading, as reflected in the stress–strain curves obtained from these tests (Figure S5a, Supporting Information). The samples C410 and C500 exhibited stress–strain curves very similar to elastic organic foams, with three characteristic deformation regimes (Figure S5b, Supporting Information): (i) an initial linear elastic region (up to 2%–4% strain), (ii) a plateau stress (extended up to $\approx 10\%$ – 12%), and (iii) a final densification stage.^[46,47] Such mechanical behavior could be attributed to the softer nature of the low-temperature carbon as observed in bulk materials. The low mechanical stiffness and the presence of organic residues could have led to plastic bending or buckling of the struts after reaching the yield stress, resulting in the plateau stress region, as typically observed in organic cellular materials.^[47,48] When the plastic collapse was completed, the struts might have started interacting with each other, leading to the rapid increase by a further slight increase in strain, causing the densification region.

The PyC material obtained at 600 °C also showed similar mechanical behavior, although several abrupt drops in stress emerged in the plateau region, suggesting brittle failure of individual PyC struts. This phenomenon became more pronounced for the samples pyrolyzed at 700 °C, where, after the elastic limit, progressive fracture of PyC struts became evident. No clear plateau stress or densification region could be distinguished at this stage. This transition from an elastic/plastic softer carbon to a brittle material with increasing temperature was due to the enhanced stiffness of the bulk material, driven by the microstructural evaluation.

At 800 and 900 °C, the 3D PyC structures completely behaved like brittle material, as sudden and substantial drops in stress could be observed in the stress–strain curve (Figure S5a, Supporting Information). The lattice structures experienced brittle fractures abruptly at the contact point of the applied load, often leading to complete catastrophic failure of the entire structure, as shown in the case of sample C800. In some cases, catastrophic failure occurred layer-by-layer, leading to a more progressive structural failure, as demonstrated for C900.

The compressive modulus of the PyC lattice structures was determined from the slope of the stress–strain curve in their elastic region. As shown in Figure S5b, the slope increased with pyrolysis temperature, indicating an increase in structural stiffness. The compressive modulus values are plotted in Figure 4c, which enhanced significantly from 26.3 ± 2.0 MPa at 410 °C to 461.7 ± 43.4 MPa at 900 °C. The elastic modulus of an architected material depends on the modulus of the constituent material, lattice geometry, and structural density.^[46] In this case, the structural density of the 3D PyC structures remained relatively constant across different pyrolysis temperatures (Figure S6, Supporting Information). This is mainly due to a balance between mass loss and volumetric shrinkage within this temperature range. As a result, the compressive modulus of our 3D PyC was majorly governed by the modulus of the bulk

material, explaining its strong correlation with the pyrolysis temperature. A similar trend was also observed for the specific modulus, which increased from 64.67 ± 10.02 kN.m Kg⁻¹ at 410 °C to 956.36 ± 116.42 kN.m Kg⁻¹ at 900 °C (Figure 4c). The compressive strength also exhibited a strong dependence on the pyrolysis temperature, as shown in Figure 4d. The compressive strength increased with pyrolysis temperature, ranging from $\approx 1.1 \pm 0.5$ MPa at 410 °C to 27.8 ± 7.7 MPa at 900 °C, reflecting progressive densification and graphitization of the carbon structure. It should be noted that the standard deviations in the compressive strength values are relatively large across all samples. Such variability could be attributed to the inherent structural variability of the microlattice architecture, including microcracks, edge defects, and localized stress concentrations, all of which contribute to variability in brittle failure behavior under compression.

Notably, the elastic modulus of bulk PyC, as measured from nanoindentation, matches that of natural bone material (15–40 GPa).^[3,49] While the PyC microlattice architectures exhibited lower mechanical values due to their porous structure, the measured compressive strength and modulus place them well within the range of trabecular bone, which typically features compressive strength of 0.1–30 MPa and modulus values of 10–3000 MPa, depending on anatomical site and porosity.^[4,50] These values make them suitable for nonload-bearing or cancellous bone repair, where mechanical support and open porosity for vascularization are essential. In comparison, widely used polymeric scaffold materials such as polylactic acid (PLA) and poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) typically exhibit bulk moduli below 100 MPa,^[3] which limits their ability to replicate the mechanical environment of native bone. In contrast, ceramic scaffolds (e.g., hydroxyapatite, alumina) can match or exceed bone stiffness but suffer from brittleness and poor processability, making it difficult to replicate the intricate, interconnected porosity required for bone integration and load distribution.

Importantly, both stiffness and strength scale with pyrolysis temperature, enabling tailored mechanical properties. Furthermore, the mechanical performance could be significantly enhanced by transitioning to higher-resolution nanolattice designs or denser lattice architectures,^[9] which would reduce structural porosity while maintaining architectural control. Such modifications, combined with high-temperature graphitization, could enable the mechanical properties to approach those of cortical bone (10–30 GPa stiffness, 100–200 MPa strength^[4]), broadening the applicability of PyC scaffolds to include load-bearing bone tissue engineering applications in the future.

2.7. Interaction of MC3T3-E1 Preosteoblast Cells within 3D PyC Scaffolds

The potential of 3D PyC microlattice structures for bone tissue engineering was evaluated by culturing MC3T3-E1 preosteoblast cells within the PyC architectures and assessing cellular viability, adhesion, and their morphological adaptation. The interaction between the PyC architectures and MC3T3-E1 cells was first evaluated using confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) and SEM. CLSM images revealed well-distributed cells across PyC microlattices (Figures 5a, d, and g), indicating effective cell

adhesion and spreading on all the PyC scaffolds, irrespective of their pyrolysis temperature. Notably, the cells extended across multiple lattice elements, demonstrating the capability of the scaffolds to support spatial cell colonization and leading to three-dimensional cell spreading. This is crucial, as the scaffolds not only provided a suitable surface for the cells to adhere to but also a 3D microenvironment conducive to cellular infiltration and 3D tissue formation. The 3D spatial distribution of the cells is further represented in Supplementary movies M1, M2, and M3 for all the scaffolds.

SEM images further confirmed these observations, where a detailed view of the cell morphology and their distributions across the lattices is presented (Figure 5). The cells were sprawled and elongated along the lattice surfaces, adopting a stretched polygonal morphology (see Figure 5i and Figure S7, Supporting Information as close-up examples), which is associated with enhanced cytoskeletal organization and cell proliferation.^[51] The stretching of the cells was extended between two or multiple lattice elements (Figures 5b,e,h and Figure S8, Supporting Information), suggesting a strong affinity to the PyC surface and potential interactions through filopodia and lamellipodia-mediated anchoring. On many occasions, the cells even uniformly covered the PyC lattices, forming a monolayer over the struts of the lattices (see Figures 5c and f).

Close-up SEM images on the adhesion sites revealed tightly anchored cellular membranes and filopodia extensions, which grasped and wrapped around the PyC lattices. Such characteristics indicate suitable biocompatibility and active cell-material interaction, as filopodia formation is a hallmark of surface exploration and initial cell adhesion.^[52,53] Interestingly, the filopodial spreading seemed more prominent for the PyC scaffolds obtained at 900 °C (Figure S9, Supporting Information), although no

significant variation in surface morphology was observed across the scaffold types. However, such observation is speculative, as direct quantification of the filopodial adhesion sites was very challenging, considering the cylindrical nature of each strut and conformational coverage of the cells over these struts.

2.8. Proliferation of MC3T3-E1 Preosteoblast Cells within 3D PyC Scaffolds

The ability of biomaterial scaffolds to sustain cell proliferation is fundamental in bone tissue engineering, as successful bone regeneration requires a suitable environment for osteoblast expansion and differentiation. To assess the capability of cells to proliferate on 3D PyC architectures, we performed a resazurin-based metabolic assay on days 1, 4, and 7 on PyC scaffolds obtained at different pyrolysis temperatures (500, 700, and 900 °C). As shown in Figure 6a, all PyC scaffolds supported MC3T3-E1 cell growth, with a progressive improvement in cellular metabolic activity over time, indicating high biocompatibility and sustained cell proliferation.

At day 1, the metabolic activity levels were similar across all the samples, suggesting a similar number of initial cell attachments on all the PyC surfaces after 24 h. By day 4, a significant increase in cell proliferation was observed for C500, whereas C700 and C900 exhibited a moderate increase in cell activity as compared to day 1. However, after 7 days of culture, all the scaffolds yielded a further significant increase in cell activity, supporting effective cell proliferation, with C500 exhibiting the highest metabolic activity and C700 and C900 yielding comparable, but slightly lower proliferation rates.

Despite the overall biocompatibility of all the scaffolds, the dependence on their properties dictated by the pyrolysis temperature was evident. The superior cell proliferation observed on C500 might be attributed to its surface chemistry. Its higher surface polarity and higher contents of oxygen functional groups (as shown in Figure S3, Supporting Information) from the remnant organic species could be attributed to the superior cell proliferation on C500. Previous studies have shown that such oxygen-rich functionalities enhance surface hydrophilicity, promote protein adsorption, and improve initial cell adhesion through integrin-mediated signaling pathways, which are known to stimulate early-stage proliferation of adherent cell types like preosteoblasts.^[54–56] On the contrary, C700 and C900 yielded a delayed cell adaptation phase before active proliferation, probably due to reduced surface polarity and increased graphitization, causing alteration in cell adhesion properties and initial slower proliferation. Furthermore, the stiffer PyC surface could have initially impeded cell spreading. However, once the adaptation phase was over, the cells eventually adapted to the more rigid carbon lattice structures, leading to enhanced proliferation.

2.9. Differentiation of MC3T3-E1 Preosteoblast Cells within 3D PyC Scaffolds

The osteogenic potential of biomaterials is a critical factor in bone tissue engineering, as the scaffolds need to not only support cell adhesion but also actively support or even promote lineage commitment and extracellular matrix maturation. To evaluate

Figure 5. CLSM microscopic images (left column) and SEM images (mid and right columns) of MC3T3-E1 preosteoblast cells cultured on 3D PyC microlattice scaffolds fabricated at pyrolysis temperatures of **a–c**) 500 °C, **d–f**) 700 °C, and **g–i**) 900 °C. The cells were cultured for 7 days before imaging. In CLSM, the nucleus and cytoskeleton of the cell were stained with DAPI (cyan) and Phalloidin (red), respectively.

Figure 6. a) Proliferation of MC3T3-E1 cells on days 1, 4, and 7 on different 3D PyC scaffolds. qRT-PCR of osteoblast differentiation markers for genes encoding b) ALP, c) Runx2, d) osteocalcin (OCN), and e) collagen 1 alpha 1 (Col1A1) at 7, 14, and 21 days post-cell-seeding within different 3D PyC scaffolds. All data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation from at least $n = 3$ cell culture replicates. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post hoc test; no statistically significant differences were observed between groups ($p > 0.05$).

the capability of PyC scaffolds to support osteogenesis, we induced differentiation of MC3T3-E1 cells cultured on the scaffolds and we analyzed the gene expression profiles of key osteogenic markers, including alkaline phosphatase (ALP), runt-related transcription factor 2 (Runx2), osteocalcin (OCN), and alpha-1 type I collagen (Col1A1) at days 7, 14, and 21 using quantitative reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (qRT-PCR). As a standard 2D reference, the results for osteogenic differentiation on tissue culture polystyrene plates are provided in the Supplementary Information (Figure S10, Supporting Information). However, due to fundamental differences in surface topography, mechanical stiffness, and dimensionality between flat plastic and 3D carbon scaffolds, direct quantitative comparisons are not emphasized.

ALP is a specific protein related to bone matrix mineralization and is generally expressed during the early stage of osteogenic differentiation by MC3T3-E1 cells.^[57] After 7 days of cell culture in a differentiation medium, a pronounced expression of ALP was detected across all the scaffolds (Figure 6b), indicating active early osteogenic differentiation and mineralization onset. Cells cultured on C500 showed higher expression of ALP than on C700 and C900 scaffolds. The levels of ALP remained more or less stable during the 21 day culture, but C700 and especially C900 showed an increase in ALP expression after 14 days of culture, which may be related to the delayed cell proliferation previously observed.

Runx2 is a critical transcription factor that activates the osteoblast differentiation marker genes in osteogenic differentiation.^[57] At day 7, all the scaffolds exhibited very weak expressions of Runx2, implying that the early-stage differentiation had not yet reached a transcriptionally driven phase. However, by day 14, Runx2 expressions peaked across all the scaffolds, as shown in Figure 6c, confirming the active

osteogenic commitment phase. At day 21, the levels of Runx2 drastically decreased, which was expected as mature osteoblasts are known to downregulate Runx2 to allow further matrix mineralization.^[58] Similar to ALP, among all the PyC scaffolds, C900 yielded the highest expression of Runx2 at day 14, followed by C500 and C700.

OCN is secreted by mature osteoblasts and is associated with calcification and bone mineralization. Therefore, it is considered a late-stage marker in osteogenic differentiation.^[59] In our experiments, we observed a progressive upregulation of OCN from day 1 to day 21 for all the scaffolds (Figure 6d), suggesting continuous extracellular matrix deposition and maturation of osteoblasts. C500 and C900 exhibited the highest OCN expression at day 21, whereas C700 expressed the lowest level of OCN.

Interestingly, Col1A1, the primary structural protein in the organic matrix of bone and an indicator of extracellular matrix deposition during osteogenic differentiation,^[60] exhibited low expressions on days 7 and 14 (Figure 6e). However, by day 21, a strong and significant upregulation of Col1A1 was observed, highlighting the transition to a mature bone matrix formation phase. Here again, C900 demonstrated the highest expression of Col1A1, with C500 and C700 having comparable expressions.

It is evident that 3D PyC architectures not only supported osteogenic differentiation but also actively modulated its progression through their properties induced by the pyrolysis temperatures. Even though PyC scaffolds obtained at 500 °C exhibited the highest degree of cell proliferation, the most superior osteogenic differentiation performance was observed for C900, particularly at the late stage. The significantly higher Runx2 and Col1A1 expression levels on C900 strongly indicate that the enhanced mechanical stiffness and hardness yielded by superior graphitization of C900

might have activated mechanotransductive pathways such as the integrin-focal adhesion kinase (FAK) axis, leading to enhanced cytoskeletal tension, nuclear translocation of Runx2, and upregulation of osteogenic gene expression.^[61,62] In addition, the increased stiffness of C900 may have promoted nuclear localization of Yes-associated protein (YAP) and TAZ (transcriptional coactivator with PDZ-binding motif), which act as key mechanosensitive regulators for gene expression. Under high mechanical tension, these proteins translocate from the cytoplasm to the nucleus, where they bind to TEAD transcription factors and upregulate downstream osteogenic genes such as Runx2, ALP, and COL1A1.^[63–66] This stiffness-responsive YAP/TAZ signaling has been widely recognized for promoting osteogenic commitment and matrix mineralization in preosteoblasts and mesenchymal stem cells.^[67] This is critical for bone tissue engineering as long-term matrix deposition and mineralization are essential for successful scaffold integration and function. The high modulus of the C900 scaffolds, approaching that of native bone, is therefore likely a key factor driving the observed osteogenic gene upregulation.

Interestingly, the PyC scaffolds obtained at 500 °C also exhibited comparable osteogenic differentiation at late stages. C500 structures exhibited a strong presence of oxygen-containing surface functional groups, as shown in the XPS results (Figure 2f). This provided a strong biochemical stimulus for osteoblast proliferation, which can promote a faster colonization of the scaffolds, achieving higher cell densities and thus inducing earlier osteogenic differentiation. However, C700 displayed a relatively weaker differentiation performance throughout. This could be attributed to the suboptimal balance between surface chemistry and mechanical properties of C700, lacking the biochemical advantages of C500, while not achieving the mechanotransductive benefits of C900.

In addition to mechanical cues, the intrinsic electrical conductivity of PyC scaffolds might have also played a role in the observed osteogenic differentiation trends. The scaffold pyrolyzed at 900 °C exhibited a conductivity of $9.3 \pm 3.8 \text{ S m}^{-1}$, which is substantially higher than that of conventional polymeric scaffolds such as PLA or PLGA, and ceramic scaffolds like hydroxyapatite, all of which are typically electrically insulating. In contrast, the scaffold treated at 500 °C behaved as a near-insulator and showed lower osteogenic gene expression, despite supporting cell proliferation. This correlation suggests that electrical conductivity, along with stiffness, might have contributed to the enhanced osteoinductive behavior observed with C900. Conductive biomaterials have been shown to enhance ion exchange, facilitate cell–cell electrical signaling, and modulate membrane potential, all of which are known to activate intracellular signaling pathways, leading to improved osteogenic differentiation.^[7,68,69] Even in the absence of external stimulation, the bioelectrically active microenvironment created by conductive scaffolds can influence protein adsorption, focal adhesion formation, and gene expression. While further studies are needed to decouple electrical from mechanical effects, our findings support the hypothesis that the combined electrochemical and mechanical properties of C900 created a more favorable environment for osteogenic lineage commitment than its lower-temperature counterparts.

While gene expression analysis of osteogenic markers (ALP, Runx2, OCN, Col1A1) offers strong molecular evidence of differentiation, this study did not include functional mineralization assays such as Alizarin Red S staining. Although such assays

are standard for assessing late-stage calcium deposition, their application is challenging in the current context for two reasons. First, the inherently black and opaque surface of pyrolytic carbon, combined with the 3D porous architecture of the scaffolds, impedes accurate visualization and quantification due to poor contrast and limited light accessibility within internal pores. Second, the hierarchical pore geometry with sizes <100 μm limits the diffusion and penetration of staining agents, further reducing assay effectiveness. An alternative approach to address such limitations could be microcomputer tomography imaging, which could offer better compatibility with dark-colored, 3D porous materials and allow for spatially resolved assessment of mineral deposition. However, a detailed study is needed to validate such speculation.

3. Conclusion

In summary, this study presents a novel approach to fabricating architected PyC scaffolds through 3D printing and pyrolysis of PEGDA microlattices, offering a tunable platform for bone regeneration. We studied the pyrolysis pathways of PEGDA microlattice to gain insights into the transformation to carbon materials, and its effect on the properties of PyC materials. The pyrolysis temperature was a deterministic factor in the physicochemical properties and the biological performance of the resulting PyC architectures. Increasing the pyrolysis temperature from 410 to 900 °C converted an amorphous and heterogeneous carbon material into a more graphitic and turbostratic carbon material, enhancing its electromechanical attributes. Electrical conductivity increased by seven orders of magnitude within this temperature range, showing a transformation from an insulating carbon to an electrically conductive carbon. Furthermore, the mechanical response to compressive stress also improved, which was reflected both in the bulk materials and in the architected form. Notably, the elastic modulus and hardness of the bulk PyC material peaked at 900 °C at $36.87 \pm 2.95 \text{ GPa}$ and $5.4 \pm 0.42 \text{ GPa}$, respectively. While evaluating the biological response of PyC scaffolds for bone tissue engineering, the scaffolds pyrolyzed at 500 °C exhibited higher metabolic activity, likely due to oxygen-rich surface chemistry, supporting enhanced proliferation of MC3T3-E1 preosteoblasts. On the contrary, scaffolds fabricated at 900 °C supported robust osteogenic differentiation, driven by their high stiffness and graphitic content, which likely activate mechanotransductive pathways. These findings establish a direct link between processing conditions, scaffold properties, and cellular behavior, enabling tailored biological responses via materials engineering. Importantly, this work lays the foundation for the next generation of carbon-based biomaterials in bone repair and broader regenerative medicine, with implications for bioelectronics, mechanobiology, and multifunctional implantable platforms.

4. Experimental Section

Fabrication of 3D-Printed Carbon Microlattice Structures: The fabrication process began with the design of the microlattice scaffold. An octet unit cell was selected for this study due to its widespread use in architected materials known for their high mechanical properties. The scaffold was

designed using Creo Parametric, a computer-aided design (CAD) software. The design featured a cylindrical geometry with a diameter of 16 mm and a height of 4 mm, filled with unit cells measuring 1.2 mm in size and lattice struts with a diameter of 200 μm . The CAD file was then sliced into 10 μm thick layers using Chitobox slicing software to prepare it for 3D printing.

The photosensitive resin used for DLP 3D printing was prepared by mixing polyethylene glycol diacrylate (PEGDA, molecular weight 700; Sigma Aldrich, product number 455 008) with the photoinitiator BAPO (Phenylbis(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl)phosphine oxide; Sigma Aldrich, product number 511 447) in a 98:2 weight ratio. The mixture was stirred on a magnetic stirrer for 2 h to ensure homogeneity. The resulting PEGDA resin was then used for 3D printing with a Phrozen Mini 8 K S DLP printer. During the printing process, a layer height of 10 μm was maintained, with an exposure time of 0.7 s per layer. After printing, the structures were immersed in a 1:1 mixture of isopropanol and acetone and subjected to ultrasonication for 10 min to remove any uncured resin. The structures were dried using compressed air, followed by a final UV curing for 30 min within a UV chamber (Elegoo Mercury XS CURE Machine; power: 36 W).

The 3D-printed PEGDA lattice structures were carbonized in a horizontal tube furnace (GSL-1100X-LD, MTI Corporation, USA). The heat treatment protocol was modified from a standard procedure previously reported by the authors for the pyrolysis of organic precursors.^[13,70–72] This modified protocol consisted of seven stages: (i) heating the samples from room temperature to 300 °C at a rate of 5 °C min⁻¹; (ii) holding at 300 °C for 3 h to ensure the removal of excess gases and stabilize the precursor; (iii) further heating from 300 to 410 °C at a rate of 1 °C min⁻¹; (iv) maintaining an isothermal hold at 410 °C for 2 h; (v) heating to the final temperature at a ramp rate of 5 °C min⁻¹; (vi) holding at the final temperature for 5 h; and (vii) allowing the samples to cool naturally to room temperature. In previous protocols reported by the authors and other researchers in the field of pyrolytic carbon, a five-step pyrolysis process was typically employed. However, in this work, additional intermediate steps (iii and iv) were introduced to ensure complete carbonization and enhance the structural stability of the resulting PyC materials.^[18] The temperatures of 300 and 410 °C were selected based on TGA of 3D-printed PEGDA, corresponding to the onset of thermal degradation and the temperature at which the maximum mass loss rate occurred, respectively. The final temperature varied between 410 and 900 °C to study its effects on the material properties. The entire carbonization process was conducted under vacuum conditions, with a vacuum pressure of -0.9 mBar.

Material Characterization of 3D-Printed Structures: The TGA of 3D-printed PEGDA was performed using a thermal gravimetric analyzer (Q50, TA Instruments), with a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹ under a nitrogen atmosphere to understand the thermal degradation of the precursor, which also helped tune the pyrolysis protocol, as mentioned earlier. The volatiles evolved during the thermal degradation were analyzed in real-time by TG-FTIR. Raman spectroscopy of the samples was conducted using a Renishaw inVia micro-Raman spectrometer with a laser wavelength of 532 nm (2.33 eV). XPS measurement was conducted on a PHI VersaProbe II spectrometer with a monochromated Al K-alpha X-radiation to generate an X-ray ($h\nu = 1486.6 \text{ eV}$ at 46.7 W).

The 3D-printed samples, both before and after pyrolysis, were examined using field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM; Apreo 2S LoVac, ThermoFisher Scientific) for characterizing the dimensional features and surface morphology. TEM of the pyrolyzed samples was performed on an FEG S/TEM microscope (Talos F200X, FEI) with an accelerating voltage of 200 kV.

Characterization of Mechanical Properties: To characterize the mechanical properties of bulk PyC materials, we first printed disk structures featuring a diameter of 8 mm and a height of 4 mm. The disks were pyrolyzed at different temperatures using the protocol mentioned earlier. Nanoindentation testing of all the PyC samples was carried out on a Hysitron (Bruker) TI950 Triboindenter equipped with a three-sided pyramidal Berkovich tip with a radius of $\approx 400 \text{ nm}$. The testing was performed on flat regions of the sample surface. The indenter area function was determined by using indents on a reference fused silica sample. A total of 15 indentations were performed at different locations of each sample in load-

control mode at a maximum load of 12.5 mN, using load-hold-unload cycle times of 10–5–2 s. Finally, all data were analyzed using the Oliver and Pharr method.^[73] For the evaluation of hardness, plastic deformation is required to occur well. The hardness (H) was determined from the peak load (F) and the projected area of contact, A(h), as shown in Equation (1). To obtain the elastic modulus, the unloading portion of the load-depth curve was analyzed according to Equation (2), where S is the slope of the unloading curve.

$$H = \frac{F}{A(h)} \quad (1)$$

$$E_r = \frac{S\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{A(h)}} \quad (2)$$

The mechanical performance of the 3D-printed PyC microlattice structures was evaluated under a compressive load using a desktop Instron 5966 testing frame equipped with a 500 N load cell and a compression rate of 100 $\mu\text{m min}^{-1}$.

Characterization of Electrical Properties: The electrical conductivity of the pyrolytic carbon (PyC) samples was evaluated using a two-electrode method. Disk-shaped PyC specimens were prepared as similar to the bulk PyC samples used for nanoindentation measurements. For electrical testing, the disks were placed between two flat copper electrodes connected to a digital source meter (Keithley 2450) to apply a constant voltage. A constant axial pressure was applied using a screw-clamp setup to ensure good electrical contact between the electrodes and the PyC surface. The resistance values (R) were directly recorded from the digital multimeter. All measurements were performed at room temperature under ambient conditions. Electrical conductivity (σ) was then determined using Equation (3), which correlates the thickness of the sample (L) and the cross-sectional area (A) of the PyC samples.

$$\sigma = \frac{L}{RA} \quad (3)$$

Cytocompatibility and Cell Proliferation Tests on 3D PyC Scaffolds: The interaction between MC3T3-E1 preosteoblast cells and PyC scaffolds was investigated through direct cell culture experiments. A preosteoblast cell line from mouse calvarial MC3T3-E1 subclone 4 (ATCC CRL-2593) was cultured in a complete medium, consisting of alpha-MEM medium (Invitrogen, USA) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (Invitrogen, USA) and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (Invitrogen, USA) at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂. Cells at passages 11–13 were used, and the medium was refreshed every two days until it reached 90% confluence.

In the meantime, for the direct tests, PyC scaffolds were prepared first by autoclaving for 40 min at 121 °C. The sterilized scaffolds were then immersed in the complete medium without any cells in a 48 well-plate and incubated for 24 h at 37 °C to promote protein adsorption on the PyC lattice surfaces. Subsequently, 10 000 cells suspended in 50 μl of complete medium were directly seeded onto each PyC scaffold for 30 mins. 300 μl of complete medium was further added to each well to immerse the samples fully. The cell-seeded PyC scaffolds were then incubated at 37 °C for 7 days.

Cell proliferation within the PyC scaffolds was assessed using a Resazurin-based metabolic assay on days 1, 4, and 7. We first prepared a 10% Resazurin solution (Labbox labware, Spain) in a complete medium. The cells/scaffolds were washed twice with phosphate buffered saline (PBS) solution and finally immersed in the 10% Resazurin solution and incubated for 6 h at 37 °C. After incubation, the Resazurin solutions were collected in a separate well plate. The cells/scaffolds were washed twice with PBS and resuspended in a fresh complete culture medium for continued incubation. Absorbance measurements at 570 nm (using 600 nm reference wavelength) were recorded for the Resazurin extracts using a spectrophotometer (Tecan Infinite Mplex). The metabolic activity of the cells was calculated by the difference in the absorbance measurements at 570 and 600 nm. A control well with cells but without a scaffold served

as the reference condition. Each experiment was performed in triplicate and in three individual experiments.

To facilitate the SEM imaging, on day 7 after cell seeding, the samples were washed with PBS and fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) solution (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) for 30 min. The cells were then dehydrated first through sequential ethanol concentrations in water (30%, 50%, 70%, 90%, and 100%) and then through sequential hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS, Sigma Aldrich, Germany) concentrations in ethanol (33%, 50%, 66%, and 100%), for 10 min each solution, followed by overnight air drying. The samples were sputter-coated with 50 nm gold and observed using a scanning electron microscope (Apreo 25 LoVac, ThermoFisher Scientific).

Additionally, cell morphology and cytoskeletal organization were analyzed using confocal microscopy. A separate set of cell-seeded scaffolds was fixed with 4% PFA for 30 min, then permeabilized with 0.1% Triton X-100 (Sigma, Germany) for 10 min. The cytoskeleton was stained with phalloidin Alexa 488 (Invitrogen, USA) and the nuclei with DAPI (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) at dilutions of 1:300 and 1:1000, respectively. Samples were incubated for one hour in the dark at room temperature, rinsed with PBS, and visualized using a confocal laser scanning microscope (Olympus FV3000, Japan) under an accelerated voltage of 3–5 kV.

Cell Differentiation Experiments Using qRT-PCR: The effect of PyC scaffolds on osteogenic differentiation was evaluated by quantifying the expressions of key osteogenic genes (ALP, Runx2, OCN, and Col1A1) at days 7, 14, and 21 using qRT-PCR. Differentiation experiments were conducted in a differentiation medium, prepared by supplementing the complete culture medium with 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ ascorbic acid, 0.1 μM dexamethasone, and 10 mM β -glycerophosphate (all from Sigma Aldrich). Cells were first seeded within the 3D PyC scaffolds as described in the proliferation experiments. After 24 h of culturing the cells, the complete medium was replaced with the same amount of differentiation medium for continued incubation. The medium was refreshed every two days. A control sample without any scaffold in the differentiation medium was also used in each culture plate. On the designated day, cells were fixed using 4% PFA, as described before, to proceed with RNA collection.

Cells were cultured for 7, 14, and 21 days in control, and scaffolds were collected in a lysis buffer containing β -mercaptoethanol (Fisher Scientific) and repeatedly passing the lysate through a 20-gauge needle at least ten times following RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen) instructions. The extracted RNA was stored at -80°C until further analysis. RNA purity and concentration were assessed using the NanoQuant Plate in a microplate reader (TECAN Infinite 200 Pro). Equal amounts of RNA from each sample were used for reverse transcription, following the QuantiTect Reverse Transcription kit (Qiagen) instructions. qRT-PCR was conducted using the RealQ Plus 2 \times Master Mix Green (Isogen) on a StepOnePlus Real-Time PCR system (Applied Biosystems). The specific primers (IDT) used for amplification are listed in **Table 2**.

The qRT-PCR protocol involved an initial polymerase activation step at 95°C for 15 min, followed by 40 cycles of denaturation and extension at 95°C for 20 s and 60°C for 1 min. A melting curve analysis was conducted at the end of the run to verify product specificity. Gene expression levels were quantified using the delta-delta Ct ($\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}$) method. The cycle threshold (Ct) values of the target genes were normalized to the housekeeping gene GAPDH (ΔCt), and the relative mRNA expression was calculated by comparing each sample to the control sample at day 1, generating $\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}$

values. The fold change in gene expression was determined using the formula: Fold increase = $2^{-\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}}$.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Monsur Islam: conceptualization (lead); data curation (lead); formal analysis (lead); funding acquisition (equal); investigation (lead); methodology (lead); project administration (lead); resources (lead); supervision (lead); validation (lead); visualization (lead); writing—original draft (lead); writing—review & editing (lead). **Jesús Ordoño:** formal analysis (supporting); investigation (supporting); methodology (supporting); validation (supporting); writing—review & editing (supporting). **Wei Tang:** formal analysis (supporting); validation (supporting); writing—review & editing (supporting). **Miguel Monclús:** data curation (supporting); formal analysis (supporting); validation (supporting); writing—review & editing (supporting). **Mónica Echeverry-Rendón:** formal analysis (supporting); investigation (supporting); supervision (supporting); validation (supporting); writing—review & editing (supporting). **De-Yi Wang:** funding acquisition (equal); investigation (supporting); project administration (equal); supervision (equal); writing—review & editing (supporting).

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

Keywords

3D printing, architected scaffolds, bone tissue engineering, microlattices, pyrolysis, pyrolytic carbon

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Table 2. Primer pair sequences used for PCR analysis.

Gene	Forward 5' \rightarrow 3'	Reverse 5' \rightarrow 3'
ALP	GCCTTCTCATCCAGTTCGTAT	CAAGGACATCGCATATCAGCTA
Runx2	CCGTCCACTGTCACTTTAATAGC	GTAGCCAGGTTCAACGATCTG
OCN	CTTTCTGCTCACTCTGCTG	TATTGCCCTCTGCTTGG
Col1A1	CATTGTGTATGCAGCTGACTTC	CGCAAAGAGTCTACATGTCTAGG
GAPDH	AATGGTGAAGCTCGGTGTG	GTGGACTCATACTGGAAACATGTAG

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